

International Journal of Advance Robotics & Expert Systems (JARES)

<https://airccse.com/jares/index.html>

<https://airccse.com/jares/vol1.html>

Current Issue, Volume 1, Number 6

INCREASING THE TRUST AND SECURITY BETWEEN AUTOMOTIVE ACTORS USING A BLOCKCHAIN IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS

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OBJECT TRACKING BASED ON BAYESIAN MONTE CARLO EMPLOYING PARTICLE GAUSSIAN INFORMATION FILTER

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